

A Short Note on the Recently Published Articles in Annals Of Clinical and Laboratory Research

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Abstract

Our main is to bring together all the articles and their scope under one roof, the annals of clinical and laboratory research is a peer review journal that bring all the advancements in the clinical research. Our main motto is to keep the information or knowledge up to date so that it will be easily conveyed to the readers of our journal.

Keywords: Pregnancy, Sperm, Ultrasound, Hysteroscopy, Methotrexate

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Introduction

Management of live cervical ectopic pregnancy this article was published in the volume 8 issue 1 it was written by the author Dr. Nnadozie Igbokwe who is specialized in the department of Obstetrics and Gynecology. This is a case report the author presents the case of live cervical ectopic pregnancy (CEP) at 6 weeks gestation. 36 years patient was presented with the mild bleeding in the vagina. She was active with serum B-hCG of 10713. The doctors performed the transvaginal ultrasound lives cervical ectopic pregnancy with a fetal pole measuring 7.1 mm and yolk sac with negative sliding sign and a empty uterus. She was then counselled and had hysteroscopy and surgical evacuation under ultrasound guidance with no complications and post-operative methotrexate injection.

The Use of Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) and track and trace technology in reducing the risks and cost of sperm cryopreservation this work was presented by Dr. Nnadozie Igbokwe who was specialized in the department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology. The main aim of the study is to know the use of radio frequency identification and track and trace technology reduce the risks and cost of sperm cryopreservation and found that no significant effect of Radio Frequency Identification on sperm mortality but with the temperature increase the sperm motility and velocity was reduced with time.

Spiral arterial morphology in relation to hypertension in

pregnancy and birth weight by placental bed biopsy: a retrospective analysis this a great work presented by Dr. assess the extent of spiral vessel dilation in hypertensive

Himleena Gautam who is specialized In the department of Obstetrics and Gynecology. The main aim of the study is to pregnancies and IUGR cases. The author concluded that spiral arterial remodeling absence is a crucial factor in low birth weight babies and hypertension in pregnancy. Furthermore research is needed to help us prevent the hypertension in pregnancy.

Convalescent plasma therapy for prophylaxis and treatment of covid-19: a systematic research of facts and files, a narrative review. The article was presented by Abhishek Singh Nayyar who is specialized in the department of Oral Medicine and Radiology. The main aim of the study is to review the covalent plasma therapy used in the treatment of COVID-19. The author reviewed various articles on covid 19 and the plasma therapy from various countries.

Biochemical test of serum ceruloplasmin as a biomarker for early detection of Oral Potentially Malignant Epithelial Lesions (PMELs) and Oral Squamous Cell Carcinoma (OSCC). This a great work written by Abhishek Singh Nayyar who is specialized in the department of Oral Medicine and Radiology. The main aim of the study is to evaluate the efficacy of serum ceruloplasmin levels as a potential biomarker in the detection oral potentially malignant epithelial lesions and frank oral cancers at a very early stage.

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